

What About Emotions? Guiding Fine-Grained Emotion Extraction from Mobile App Reviews

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Abstract—Opinion mining plays a vital role in analysing user feedback and extracting insights from textual data. While most research focuses on sentiment polarity (e.g., positive, negative, neutral), fine-grained emotion classification in app reviews remains underexplored. Fine-grained emotion classification is thus needed to better understand users’ affective responses and support downstream tasks such as feature-emotion analysis, user-oriented release planning, and issue triaging. This paper addresses this gap by identifying and addressing the challenges and limitations in fine-grained emotion analysis in the context of app reviews. Our study adapts Plutchik’s emotion taxonomy to app reviews by developing a structured annotation framework and dataset. Through an iterative human annotation process, we define clear annotation guidelines and document key challenges in emotion classification. Additionally, we evaluate the feasibility of automating emotion annotation using large language models, assessing their cost-effectiveness and agreement with human-labelled data. Our findings reveal that while large language models significantly reduce manual effort and maintain substantial agreement with human annotators, full automation remains challenging due to the complexity of emotional interpretation. This work contributes to opinion mining in requirements engineering by providing structured guidelines, an annotated dataset, and insights for developing automated pipelines to capture the complexity of emotions in app reviews.

Index Terms—mobile apps, app reviews, emotions, opinion mining, annotation, dataset, large language models

I. INTRODUCTION

Mining app reviews from mobile app repositories has gained significant attention in requirements engineering (RE) research over the past decade [1]. Relevant descriptors from mobile app reviews include numerical rating [2], review type [3] (e.g., *bug report*, *feature request*, *praise*), topic [4] (e.g., *usability*, *design*, *security*), and polarity [5] (e.g., *positive*, *neutral*, *negative*). The combined use of these descriptors has led to advanced methods for requirements elicitation [6] and validation [7] tasks, such as aspect-based sentiment analysis [8] and feature-based opinion mining [9].

Among these, polarity has emerged as one of the most widely used descriptors in app review analysis [9], [3], [10], [11], [12], and it continues to attract significant attention in recent studies [13], [14], [15]. Polarity is defined as the overall sentiment expressed in user feedback, leading to the classification of textual content into predefined sentiment

categories, typically *positive*, *neutral*, or *negative*. Despite its popularity, automatic polarity measurement still presents significant cognitive challenges, such as subtle sentiments, sarcasm, and domain-specific language. These lead to limited precision and low recall in negative feedback [2], [8].

In addition to these challenges, polarity-based opinion mining lacks the granularity to capture nuanced emotions in user feedback. Polarity labels fail to convey the depth of emotions tied to feature-based opinions, limiting their usefulness for fine-grained analysis. For instance, consider the following *positive* reviews:

[R₁] *Useful app which follows Material Design.*

[R₂] *Awesome team work but this application does need updating now*

[R₃] *I run it on my Dropbox cloud storage with Android, Mac and Linux, and I have had no issues*

In addition to its inherent positivity, [R₁] highlights the user’s excitement about a specific characteristic. In contrast, [R₂] conveys a user request or suggestion for a change or update of the app. Finally, [R₃] reflects the user’s acceptance and personal experience with a particular feature.

Likewise, consider the following *negative* reviews:

[R₄] *My only complaint is that I sometimes have sync issues with shared notebooks.*

[R₅] *I really didn’t want to make this app my default SMS messaging app on my phone.*

[R₆] *Very invasive, [...] was forcing to update from a third party store and it wanted to access everything on your phone including your SIM card data.*

In addition to its inherent negativity, [R₄] conveys minor user disappointment due to issues or bugs with a specific feature. In contrast, [R₅] reflects the user’s outright rejection and decision to stop using the app, which the user considers not suited for purpose. Finally, [R₆] highlights the user’s lack of trust stemming from critical safety and privacy concerns.

This limitation in expressiveness motivates our research. We propose to use *emotion labels* to better capture the nuanced emotional states conveyed in user feedback, allowing more

informed and targeted decision-making. This enables use cases such as fine-grained feature-oriented emotion analysis to better prioritize or refine specific app functionalities, and market analysis to categorize user feedback more effectively by emotional trends in terms of user satisfaction and adoption.

Fine-grained emotion analysis has been explored in opinion mining tasks in various review types, such as products [16], movies [17] and books [18]. However, emotion analysis research in app reviews remains scarce, particularly in the context of mobile app reviews. This entails several limitations in the state of the art: lack of guidelines for human annotators, ignorance on the challenges they face during the annotation process, and lack of public datasets for multiclass emotion extraction, among others. Moreover, the opportunities large language models (LLMs) offer to perform this task remain unknown.

In this research, we address all these aspects and as a result, we present the following contributions:

- C₁. The adaptation of an 8-emotion taxonomy, already used in software engineering, to the context of app reviews.
- C₂. A set of guidelines and instructions to support the manual annotation of emotions in the context of app reviews.
- C₃. A dataset of 1,112 sentences from app reviews annotated with human emotions, belonging to 257 mobile apps.
- C₄. A set of challenges and design suggestions for the development of automated emotion extraction methods.
- C₅. Insights into the cost-effectiveness, agreement and correctness of LLM-based annotations with respect to humans.

A replication package including datasets and source code is openly shared (See *Data Availability Statement*).

Our work lays the groundwork for fine-grained emotion extraction from mobile app reviews, providing a structured dataset, annotation guidelines, and design recommendations for automated methods. By leveraging human annotations alongside LLMs, we assess the feasibility of reducing manual effort in emotion classification while maintaining annotation quality. We expect our findings to guide future research on automating emotion extraction in software reviews more broadly, facilitating its integration into RE processes for improved user feedback analysis.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Emotion Analysis

Recent advances in natural language processing have sparked growing research interest in opinion mining to support software engineering processes [19]. Moreover, emotional aspects have been extensively explored in the context of RE tasks [20], including elicitation [21], [22], [23], specification [24] and validation [25]. Specifically, analysing user feedback from software-related reviews has also emerged as a key approach to integrating emotional aspects into RE [26], [17], [18]. These studies vary in scope and purpose, ranging from analysing app usage experience [27] to classifying emotional states from user feedback on social media platforms [28], [29].

Studies on emotion analysis rely on well-established *emotion taxonomies* – structured classifications of emotions based

on psychological theories. These taxonomies vary in scope, granularity, and theoretical foundations across disciplines, making their selection crucial to capturing the necessary level of detail for a given task. While some frameworks define a small set of basic emotions [30], [31], [32], others introduce finer distinctions with broader emotional states [33], reflecting diverse perspectives on how emotions are structured and expressed. In the context of app reviews, opinion mining has mainly focused on polarity-based analysis [9], [34], while fine-grained classifications are more common in other domains such as clinical and psychological studies [35]. Bridging this gap requires adopting emotion taxonomies that balance granularity and applicability to the analysis of app reviews, as explored by prior work (see Section VI).

B. Annotation Strategies in User Feedback

The reliability of annotations in user feedback depends on the annotation strategy, which can be categorized into expert-based, crowdsourced, and automated methods.

Expert-based annotation, performed by domain specialists or trained annotators, provides high-quality labels through structured guidelines and domain knowledge. Studies on app review analysis, using Cohen’s and Fleiss Kappa metrics [36], report *moderate* (0.41 – 0.60) to *substantial* (0.61 – 0.80) inter-annotator agreement, typically with Kappa values ranging from 0.60 to 0.70 for tasks such as feature extraction [2] and sentiment analysis [2], [37]. However, expert annotation is costly and time-intensive, limiting scalability. Additionally, cognitive challenges in app review interpretation can limit the usefulness of human-annotated datasets to support automatic extraction, especially for descriptors such as review helpfulness, leading to *slight* (0.00 – 0.20) agreement [38].

Crowdsourced annotation utilizes non-expert contributors to label data at scale. Prior work has used crowdsourcing to validate unsupervised features and other descriptors in mobile app reviews [39], [8]. Beyond app reviews, crowdsourcing is widely used in the context of RE [40], [41], [42]. While efficient, it often leads to *moderate* agreement due to annotator subjectivity and domain unfamiliarity [43], [44], [45].

Automated methods leverage machine learning models or LLMs to generate annotations without human intervention [46]. While scalable, their reliability depends on model performance and training data quality. Some studies show comparable agreement levels between model-generated annotations and expert labels, particularly when fine-tuning encoder-based models on domain-specific data [47]. However, automated approaches lack human intuition, struggle with ambiguity, and may propagate biases from training data [48]. Consequently, expert annotation remains the gold standard.

In this study, we focus on expert-based labelling, guided by structured annotation guidelines, to ensure high-quality annotations. Due to the cognitive complexity of adapting emotions to app reviews, we exclude crowdsourced annotation. Finally, as LLMs demonstrate increasing effectiveness in text classification and annotation tasks [46], we explore their potential as automated annotators in this context.

III. METHOD

A. Design

The goal of this research is to **identify and address the challenges and limitations of fine-grained emotion analysis in mobile app reviews**. Our study focuses on the adaptation of an emotion taxonomy, the analysis of the complexities of human annotation, and the reliability of LLMs for automated annotation. The following use cases illustrate how this fine-grained emotion analysis can support RE-related feedback gathering tasks by uncovering insights beyond traditional polarity-based analysis.

- UC₁. Categorizing feature-related feedback.** Identify distinct emotional responses tied to specific features, such as whether users struggle with usability, expect improvements, express confusion, or show appreciation.
- UC₂. Emotion-based user segmentation for release planning.** Segment user feedback by emotion types to understand how different user groups emotionally respond to recent updates or unmet expectations. This supports planning future releases that align better with user sentiment dynamics across versions or personas.
- UC₃. Prioritizing critical issues based on emotional risk.** Analyse high arousal reviews (e.g., anger over privacy violations, fear about data loss, or betrayal due to broken trust) to prioritize and address issues with higher potential for reputational or legal consequences.

To achieve this goal and support the outlined use cases, we issue the following research questions (RQ):

- RQ₁.** Which taxonomy of emotions is most suitable for annotating mobile app reviews?
- RQ₂.** How can the selected taxonomy be effectively adapted to the specific context of app reviews?
- RQ₃.** What challenges arise when humans manually annotate app reviews with emotion labels?
- RQ₄.** How does LLM-based annotation compare to human annotation in emotion classification for app reviews?

Figure 1 illustrates our research design, including the steps involved in the resolution of each RQ. The figure shows how our method has produced two actionable assets, ready to be used by the RE community: (1) *annotation guidelines* to drive the manual process of annotating a set of app reviews using an emotion taxonomy; (b) an *annotated dataset* containing 1,112 app reviews annotated with the emotion taxonomy following the annotation guidelines.

To address **RQ₁**, we conducted a **literature review** on emotion and sentiment analysis in user reviews. We extended the scope beyond mobile app reviews to software-related reviews for broader generalizability. This led to the selection of a suitable *emotion taxonomy* as the foundation for annotation.

To address **RQ₂**, we implemented an **iterative human annotation** process based upon *annotation guidelines* using a subset of a publicly available app reviews dataset [39]. Feedback from each iteration served to refine the annotation guidelines, including definitions, instructions, and examples

for identifying emotions in app reviews. These guidelines were used to generate the final *annotated dataset*.

To address **RQ₃**, we analysed **human agreement** during the annotation process. For each iteration, we computed the pairwise Kappa agreement among annotators and examined confusion matrices to detect label-specific interpretation conflicts. We analysed also the discussions held to resolve these conflicts, which served for clarifying biases or refining guidelines. This process identified key *annotation challenges*, guiding the design of automatic emotion extraction tasks.

To address **RQ₄**, we designed an **LLM-based annotation** process, selecting and comparing state-of-the-art LLMs with advanced analytical capabilities. Our analysis focused on two dimensions: (1) cost-efficiency and (2) agreement, assessing inter-rater reliability between human and LLM annotations, as well as LLM prediction correctness against human ground truth. This resulted in a *human vs. LLM annotation analysis*, laying the groundwork for LLM-based emotion extraction from app reviews and AI-based annotation in related tasks.

Details of the methodology used in the four RQs follow.

B. Literature Review

We constructed our search string by integrating two key areas: *emotion analysis* and *software reviews*. For *emotion analysis*, following Lin et al.'s approach [19], we adopted the generic term *emotion* to maximize potential matches. For *software reviews*, we included multiple synonyms such as *app*, *application*, and *API*, along with alternative phrases like *user reviews*. This resulted in the following search string:

```
("emotion*") AND ("app* review*" OR "software* review*" OR "user* review*" OR "application* review*" OR "api* review*")
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We selected Scopus for its broad coverage of high-quality, peer-reviewed research across disciplines [49], structuring the literature review into the following steps:

- **Step ① – Study collection.** We executed the defined search string in Scopus, exporting full references, metadata, and abstracts into a spreadsheet for further analysis.
- **Step ② – Inclusion and exclusion criteria (IC/EC).** Papers were included if they (i) proposed, used, or analysed a multi-class emotion taxonomy, and (ii) focused on software-related user reviews. Papers were excluded if they: (i) lacked full-text access, (ii) were not in English or Spanish, (iii) were unrelated to opinion mining, or (iv) focused solely on sentiment polarity.
- **Step ③ – Forward snowballing.** Backward snowballing was excluded as it prioritizes older studies, which may not align with the latest advancements in emotion analysis. Instead, we applied forward snowballing through Google Scholar to identify recent developments until saturation was reached, with no new relevant studies emerging.
- **Step ④ – Feature extraction.** For each selected study, we extracted key features, including taxonomy details (e.g., name, size, list of emotions), datasets (e.g., size, type, availability), emotion extraction methods (e.g., man-

Fig. 1. Research method.

ual, machine learning, deep learning), and evaluation metrics (e.g., accuracy, precision, recall).

- **Step 5 – Taxonomy inspection.** We analysed the identified emotion taxonomies both quantitatively and qualitatively. This assessment helped identify their potential benefits and limitations, ultimately guiding the selection of the most suitable taxonomy for this study.

C. Iterative Human Annotation

Human annotation takes two key artifacts as input: the **emotion taxonomy** (derived from RQ₁) and the **dataset of reviews** for annotation. We leveraged a dataset of user reviews from a multi-domain catalogue of popular mobile apps [39], spanning 10 Google Play categories. Additionally, it provides annotations for 198 distinct app features (e.g., *instant messaging*, *video sharing*, *note-taking*, *GPS navigation*), enabling future research in feature-based emotion analysis. We randomly selected up to 10 sentences from reviews mentioning each feature¹, resulting in a total of 1,412 reviews. These were shuffled and divided into 15 subsets (100 reviews each, 12 for the latter), labelled from *iteration*₀ to *iteration*₁₄. Annotations were performed by five human annotators (*Ann*₁ to *Ann*₅), all co-authors of this paper, as follows:

- **Step 6 – Guidelines elaboration.** Based on the literature review (RQ₁), *Ann*₁ drafted the initial version of the annotation guidelines. These guidelines include: (i) formal definitions of each emotion adapted to the context of mobile app reviews, (ii) real examples of app review sentences for each emotion, and (iii) detailed instructions on the annotation process. Annotation was defined at the sentence level, with emotions assigned atomically to individual sentences. Annotators could refer to full reviews for context and ambiguity resolution. The guidelines were refined during the first two iterations. In *iteration*₀, *Ann*₁ and *Ann*₂ independently labelled a shared subset of sentences without prior discussion, allowing ambiguities and gaps in the guidelines to surface.
- **Step 7 – Guidelines refinement.** Following the initial guidelines draft, all five annotators participated in a joint iteration (*iteration*₂). Involving multiple annotators

ensured diverse perspectives, helping to uncover defects, inconsistencies, ambiguities, and potential threats to validity in the annotation process. After annotation, we conducted a dedicated meeting to systematically review disagreements, linking each to a concrete action point for improving the annotation guidelines (e.g., adding examples, refining ambiguous vocabulary, clarifying criteria for distinguishing emotions).

- **Step 8 – Dataset annotation.** Once the guidelines were stabilized, we iterated over the remaining 12 subsets of reviews (*iteration*₃ → *iteration*₁₄) to create the final dataset. Three annotators (*Ann*₁, *Ann*₂, *Ann*₃) were designated as *main annotators* and two (*Ann*₄, *Ann*₅) as *secondary annotators*. Each iteration included two main annotators and one secondary annotator, rotating across all possible pairings to systematically identify and address inconsistencies. The 12 iterations were grouped into four batches (2, 4, 4, and 2 iterations, respectively). Each annotator recorded the time spent reading the guidelines and completing each iteration. Each emotion was assessed independently, meaning that a given sentence can be annotated with multiple emotions. This possibility was used with caution, i.e. only when the sentence contained sub-sentences expressing different emotions. The final annotation retained emotion labels that at least two of the three annotators involved in the iteration agreed upon.

D. Human Agreement

After each iteration, we measured annotator agreement, analysed disagreements, and refined the guidelines to improve annotation consistency. This process was structured as follows:

- **Step 9 – Pairwise Kappa analysis.** We used Cohen’s Kappa to assess pairwise agreement between annotators in each iteration. Unlike Fleiss’ Kappa, pairwise Cohen’s Kappa allows us to monitor individual interpretation conflicts and cognitive biases, helping to identify challenges in emotion classification from user reviews. To further analyse disagreement patterns, we also generated confusion matrices for each pair of annotators.
- **Step 10 – Agreement analysis.** As a quality control measure, we set a minimum agreement threshold of Cohen’s Kappa ≥ 0.60 (i.e., *substantial* agreement) for

¹Some features in the dataset had fewer than 10 reviews mentioning them.

each pair of annotators per iteration. Additionally, we qualitatively analysed the confusion matrices from the previous step to identify recurring disagreement patterns (e.g., frequently confused emotions, systematic biases, or inconsistencies in annotator tendencies).

- **Step 11 – Disagreement discussion.** Using Cohen’s Kappa and confusion matrices as input, we held dedicated meetings at the end of each batch to analyse major disagreement patterns. Each pattern was linked to a specific action point, akin to those proposed in Step 7. At this stage, we aimed to minimize guideline modifications to maintain consistency with previous annotations. Changes were kept limited and comparable in scope to ensure that the guidelines remained generalizable across different datasets and app domains while avoiding overstatements.

E. LLM-based Annotation

After annotation, we evaluated LLM agents using the generated guidelines as follows:

- **Step 12 – LLM-based annotation.** We evaluated the performance of three advanced LLMs with API access: GPT-4o², Mistral Large 2³, and Gemini 2.0 Flash⁴. For each, we created an LLM assistant with a system prompt embedding the annotation guidelines with additional input-output formatting instructions. We tested the models under three temperature settings: high (1), mid (0.5), and low (0). This experimental setup enables a more comprehensive evaluation of LLM performance while aligning LLM challenges with those encountered in human annotation (RQ₃). To balance efficiency and avoid performance degradation from excessively long prompts, the dataset was processed in batches of 10 reviews. Each assistant was run three times on the full dataset.
- **Step 13 – Agreement analysis.** We assessed the average pairwise agreement between humans and LLM assistants using Cohen’s Kappa. Additionally, treating the human agreement as ground truth, we evaluated LLM performance in terms of precision, recall, and F-measure.
- **Step 14 – Cost-efficiency analysis.** Using average results from three annotation runs for each LLM, we measured total token usage, including input and completion output tokens, along with the associated API cost (€). We also recorded execution times for the automated annotation process. These results were then compared to a human cost-efficiency analysis, factoring in personnel costs (€) and the time required for annotation iterations.

IV. RESULTS

A. Emotion Taxonomy (RQ₁)

Figure 2 reports the results of the literature review⁵, which identified 11 studies employing multi-class emotion taxonomies in the context of software reviews.

²<https://platform.openai.com/docs/models/gpt-4o>

³<https://mistral.ai/en/news/mistral-large-2407>

⁴<https://deepmind.google/technologies/gemini/flash/>

⁵Study collection on iteration 1 was conducted on June 1st, 2024.

Fig. 2. Results from the literature review.

No single taxonomy has been universally adopted for emotion analysis in software reviews. Three studies [50], [51], [52] utilize or adapt Plutchik’s wheel of emotions [31], which defines eight basic emotions – *Joy*, *Trust*, *Fear*, *Surprise*, *Sadness*, *Disgust*, *Anger*, and *Anticipation* – while also modeling relationships between emotions and their arousal levels (i.e., intensity of emotional experience). Two studies [53], [37] employ variations of Parrott’s taxonomy [32], which identifies six basic emotions. Five of these emotions (*Joy*, *Fear*, *Surprise*, *Sadness*, and *Anger*) align with Plutchik’s, while *Love* is introduced as a distinct category. One study [54] applies Ekman’s taxonomy [30], which includes *Happy*, *Sadness*, *Surprise*, *Fear*, and *Anger*, overlapping with both Plutchik’s and Parrott’s models. Additionally, it incorporates *Disgust*, consistent with Plutchik’s classification. Another study [55] utilizes Liew and Turtle’s taxonomy, which defines 28 fine-grained emotions, including *Admiration*, *Doubt*, *Pride*, and *Jealousy*, providing a more granular categorization of emotional expressions in software reviews. Finally, four studies [56], [16], [57], [58] employed custom emotion taxonomies. These approaches included reusing emotions from existing taxonomies [57], adapting taxonomies to align with the syntax required by a third-party emotion extraction tool [16], [58], or defining a domain-specific set of emotions [56].

Fig. 3. Distribution of emotions in the literature review (including only those that appear in more than one study).

We collected all identified emotions and applied minimal normalization, which involved standardizing syntax by converting words to their root forms. Using normalized data, we generated Figure 3 to illustrate the frequency of emotions studied in software reviews. Based on this analysis, we chose Plutchik’s Wheel of Emotions not only because it is the most used in the papers found, but also for the following reasons. First, its eight basic emotions are among the nine most studied, the only exception being *Love*. Second, Plutchik’s model defines opposite emotion pairs and incorporates contiguous

emotions, making it easier to compare emotions while allowing the identification and discussion of reviews that may fall between two emotions. Finally, emotions such as *Anticipation* – unique to Plutchik’s model – can provide insights into user expectations, particularly in exploring new features, a common focus in mobile app feedback analysis [3], [9].

B. Annotation Guidelines and Annotated Dataset (RQ₂)

The outcome of RQ₂ consists of two artifacts: (1) the *annotation guidelines*, and (2) the *annotated dataset*.

1) *Annotation guidelines*: A 10-page document including formal definitions of each of the Plutchik’s eight primary emotions adapted to the mobile app review domain, alongside 48 annotated review sentence examples. Table I summarizes (partially) the content of these guidelines, which are fully detailed in our replication package. In addition to Plutchik’s emotions, during this process we elicited two additional labels for the annotation task: *Neutral*, restricted to sentences reflecting purely objective content without expressing any particular emotion linked to the current state of the app; and *Reject*, restricted to sentences that cannot be interpreted from a linguistic standpoint.

2) *Annotated dataset*: A dataset of 1,272 annotated labels, including emotions, neutral, and rejected cases, assigned to 1,112 sentences from distinct reviews. Table I includes the distribution for each emotion in the final dataset, in addition to 88 neutral sentences and 22 rejected sentences.

C. Annotation Challenges (RQ₃)

Figure 4 summarizes the evolution of the average Cohen’s Kappa agreement for each annotator across iterations following the process described in Sections III-C and III-D.

Fig. 4. Evolution of the average Cohen’s Kappa agreement across iterations.

After the initial version of the guidelines produced by *Ann₁* and *Ann₂* in *iteration₁*, the team inter-rater agreement grew progressively from *moderate* at the start of the process (average Cohen’s Kappa of 0.52 in *iteration₂*) to *substantial* at the end (average Cohen’s Kappa of 0.69 for all iterations involving the dataset annotation). Notably, all pairwise agreements from *iteration₃* onward remained above the *substantial* agreement threshold (dotted red line). Fluctuations in early iterations suggest ongoing adjustments into the guidelines, while later stability reflects the effectiveness of iterative refinement. The final iteration showed higher agreement but involved only

12 reviews, making it less representative. Complementarily, we also analysed average Cohen’s Kappa scores for individual emotion labels. Results show that *Joy*, *Anticipation*, and *Reject* labels achieved the highest agreement, while *Surprise*, *Anger*, and *Disgust* exhibited the lowest consistency. Expanded label-specific agreement is available in the replication package.

During this process, we experienced a number of challenges in adapting Plutchik’s taxonomy to mobile app reviews and developed mitigation strategies, either incorporated into the guidelines or applied during annotation. We summarize the key outcomes below:

- **Challenge 1. Defining boundaries between contiguous emotions.** Contiguous emotions in Plutchik’s taxonomy share overlapping attributes, leading to consistent disagreements among annotators. For instance, in the sentence “*I just love this notebook*”, *Ann₂* and *Ann₃* labelled it as *Joy*, reflecting app appraisal, while *Ann₅* assigned *Trust*, interpreting it as a personal involvement. Similarly, in “[...] *the app is saying I need to keep signing in and my notebooks aren’t retrievable*”, all annotators marked it as *Sadness*, emphasizing disappointment, while *Ann₄* labelled it as *Disgust*, focusing on rejection. To address this, we refined the guidelines with explicit disambiguation criteria for conflicting emotion pairs reporting the lowest label-specific agreement.
- **Challenge 2. Addressing mixed or conflicting emotions in a single sentence.** A sentence may express multiple, potentially conflicting emotions, such as *Joy* and *Sadness* (e.g., “*I really appreciate this app but lately I’ve been having issues with the cloud sync.*”) or *Sadness* and *Anger* (e.g., “*It wasn’t what I needed, and I absolutely HATE that they don’t even tell you the timers are for premium memberships only.*”). This complexity challenges the assumption that emotions are mutually exclusive. To address this, we allowed multiple emotions to be assigned to a single sentence, ensuring that mixed - or even conflicting - emotions are properly captured without enforcing artificial exclusivity.
- **Challenge 3. Establishing thresholds for subtle emotional intensity (arousal).** Implicit emotional expressions may be overlooked or exaggerated due to subjective interpretation. For instance, *Sadness* or disappointment can be difficult to assess (e.g., “*No calendar sync*”), and *Surprise* may depend on whether an event was truly unexpected (e.g., “*The app decided to add a folder to my gallery [...]*”). To address this, we refined our guidelines with additional examples to clarify when an emotion’s intensity meets the labeling threshold, reducing both underreporting and overinterpretation.
- **Challenge 4. Handling lack of context and linguistic ambiguities in sentence-level emotion extraction.** Eliciting emotions at the sentence level is challenging due to missing contextual information. This could potentially lead to inconsistencies, as identical sentences yield different emotions depending on their context, particularly

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF EMOTION ANNOTATION GUIDELINES. INCLUDES NUMBER OF ANNOTATED SENTENCES PER LABEL (#).

Label	#	Expresses...	Contains...	Example
Joy	372	excitement; pleasure; possibility; positiveness	app praise; features or characteristics appreciated by users	"Excellent task and list management tool"
Sadness	303	disappointment; loss; heaviness; severity	negative user experiences; reports of bugs or faults	"Just that RCS/Chat function has regular failures unfortunately."
Anticipation	182	curiosity; consideration; alertness; exploration	inquiries about app changes; feature requests; questions about uncertain aspects	"I would love a barcode scanner to be included."
Trust	151	acceptance; connection; safeness; warmth	positive user experiences; satisfaction with goals or needs; privacy and security observations	"One of the best note-taking I've tried so far"
Surprise	54	shocked; unexpected; unpredictability	unexpected user issues; unknown events or situations	"Why you made char limit in bookmark name and description???"
Disgust	49	lack of trust; rejection; bitterness; refusal	explicit rejections of the app; claims that the app is unsuitable for its purpose	"I find this app frustrating, will be using a running watch from now on"
Anger	27	fury; rage; fierceness; hate	hate speech; insults; extremely negative vocabulary	"I hate that it disconnects if the app is not running in the background"
Fear	24	stress; anxiety; agitation; scared	complaints about trust issues; requests for help with frustration or anxiety	"People are adding fake members via python by scrapping to make their group look huge."
Neutral	88	nothing	objective content; no emotions regarding current app state	"Call recording is disabled."
Reject	22	unknown	non-English text; noisy content	"Video chat ki bii suvida honi chahiy"

when linguistic ambiguities (e.g., pronouns, acronyms, or elliptical subjects) were present. To address this, annotators were instructed to label individual sentences, consulting the full review only to resolve linguistic ambiguities.

D. Human vs. LLM Annotation Analysis (RQ₄)

As described in Section III, annotation analysis between human and LLM-based performance focuses on two main dimensions: agreement and cost-efficiency analysis.

Fig. 5. Evaluation of human agreement vs. LLM-based agreement

1) *Agreement Analysis*: Figure 5 illustrates the evaluation setup, comparing human agreement (Ann_A) with LLM-based agreement (LLM_A). For each LLM included in this study, we conducted three annotation runs, deriving an agreement annotation using the same criteria applied to human agreement (see Section III-C). We then computed the agreement among individual LLMs (GPT-4o, Mistral Large 2, Gemini 2.0 Flash) to obtain the overall LLM agreement (LLM_A), which we compared against human agreement (Ann_A). Since the lowest temperature setting (0) yielded the best results, we limit the reported results to this setting.

Figure 6 reports the inter-rater pairwise Cohen’s Kappa agreement between all annotators, including five humans⁶

⁶Secondary annotators Ann_4 and Ann_5 never participated in the same iteration of the final dataset annotation ($iteration_3$ to $iteration_{14}$).

Fig. 6. Inter-rater pairwise agreement (human and LLM-based)

(Ann_i) and LLMs (GPT_A , $Mistral_A$, $Gemini_A$). It also includes agreement between each annotator and the overall human (Ann_A) and LLM-based (LLM_A) agreements. Agreement between different runs from the same LLM is excluded from this analysis, as they exhibited near-perfect consistency (pairwise Cohen’s Kappa agreement was always ≥ 0.87). On average, pairs of humans show an agreement (0.69) that is similar to the agreement shown by pairs of LLMs (0.68). However, LLM annotations (GPT_A , $Mistral_A$, $Gemini_A$) exhibit moderate agreement with human annotations (0.56 – 0.62), indicating some deviation from human judgment. Among individual models, Gemini 2.0 Flash ($Gemini_A$) aligns more closely with human agreement (Ann_A), although LLM agree-

TABLE II
LLM CORRECTNESS VS. HUMAN AGREEMENT (Ann_A)

Annotator	Precision	Recall	F1
GPT _i	68.77%	64.50%	66.57%
GPT _A	69.41%	64.92%	67.09%
Mistral _i	62.26%	61.13%	61.69%
Mistral _A	63.36%	61.71%	62.52%
Gemini _i	67.44%	67.46%	67.45%
Gemini _A	67.48%	67.59%	67.54%
LLM _A	70.68%	66.81%	68.69%

ment (LLM_A) is slightly higher. This suggests that combining multiple LLM instances helps mitigate biases, similar to how human annotators vary in judgment. GPT-4o (GPT_A) shows the highest consistency with overall LLM agreement (LLM_A), while Mistral and Gemini introduce more variability across different runs.

Using human agreement (Ann_A) as ground-truth, Table II reports the average precision, recall and F1 metrics of: individual LLM runs (GPT_i , $Mistral_i$, $Gemini_i$); agreement between LLM runs (GPT_A , $Mistral_A$, $Gemini_A$); and agreement between all LLMs (LLM_A). These results reinforce the idea that agreement between multiple LLM instances (LLM_A) is the best setting, reporting the highest F1 measure. However, the highest recall is reported by $Gemini_A$. This also opens the need to analyse alternative quality metrics, properly weighting precision and recall based on task criticality and the cost of missing relevant emotion labels [59].

TABLE III
HUMAN INDIVIDUAL CORRECTNESS VS. HUMAN AGREEMENT (Ann_A)

Annotator	Precision	Recall	F1
Ann ₁	86.96%	88.76%	87.86%
Ann ₂	88.66%	88.89%	88.78%
Ann ₃	86.14%	84.84%	85.49%
Ann ₄	85.24%	83.08%	84.16%
Ann ₅	81.97%	77.73%	79.85%
Ann _i	85.79%	84.66%	85.23%

Complementarily, and using the same criteria, Table III shows that human annotators are highly consistent with one another, with F1 scores ranging narrowly from 79.85% to 88.78% and an overall average of 85.23%. Despite having different roles in the annotation process (e.g., primary vs. secondary), all annotators achieve comparably high precision and recall, indicating strong alignment with the agreed-upon annotation guidelines. This consistency reinforces the reliability of the human-created ground truth and highlights the effectiveness of the annotation guidelines and calibration process in minimizing individual biases.

Table IV presents correctness metrics for each annotation label defined in Table I, revealing substantial differences in annotation performance across labels. The best-performing classes — *Joy*, *Sadness*, *Anticipation*, and *Reject* — exhibit

TABLE IV
LLM AGREEMENT (LLM_A) CORRECTNESS PER LABEL

Label	Precision	Recall	F1
<i>Joy</i>	73.70%	68.55%	71.03%
<i>Sadness</i>	82.48%	74.59%	78.34%
<i>Anticipation</i>	78.57%	90.66%	84.18%
<i>Trust</i>	70.91%	51.32%	59.54%
<i>Surprise</i>	41.38%	22.22%	28.92%
<i>Disgust</i>	42.86%	42.00%	42.42%
<i>Anger</i>	35.42%	62.96%	45.33%
<i>Fear</i>	38.10%	33.33%	35.56%
<i>Neutral</i>	48.15%	59.09%	53.06%
<i>Reject</i>	94.44%	77.27%	85.00%

high recall and balanced precision, suggesting that these are easier to distinguish based on the guidelines used by the LLM annotator. Notably, these labels also show the highest human agreement (RQ_3), reinforcing their clearer annotation boundaries. Conversely, *Surprise*, *Disgust*, *Anger*, and *Fear* show the lowest performance, both in terms of correctness and label-specific human agreement, with frequent misclassifications. Additionally, *Anger* has relatively high recall but very low precision, indicating it is often over-predicted, whereas *Surprise* suffers from poor recall, suggesting the model struggles to identify it. These discrepancies highlight the challenges LLMs face in distinguishing subtle or less frequently expressed emotions (*Challenge 3* in RQ_3). Overall, these findings emphasize the need for refined annotation guidelines and model adaptations, such as class-specific confidence thresholds or multi-label classification approaches.

TABLE V
AVERAGE HUMAN INDIVIDUAL (Ann_i) CORRECTNESS PER LABEL

Label	Precision	Recall	F1
<i>Joy</i>	90.99%	91.37%	91.18%
<i>Sadness</i>	89.36%	82.67%	86.02%
<i>Anticipation</i>	88.71%	88.72%	88.71%
<i>Trust</i>	85.23%	81.37%	83.30%
<i>Surprise</i>	64.07%	74.56%	69.31%
<i>Disgust</i>	68.98%	72.62%	70.80%
<i>Anger</i>	69.07%	77.21%	73.14%
<i>Fear</i>	74.15%	78.50%	76.32%
<i>Neutral</i>	78.41%	76.06%	77.24%
<i>Reject</i>	82.00%	89.46%	85.73%

Table V shows the average correctness of individual human annotators per emotion label. While humans also find emotions like *Surprise*, *Disgust*, *Anger*, and *Fear* more challenging, their performance remains stable and never drops to the critical levels seen in LLM outputs. In contrast, LLMs significantly underperform on these emotions, with pronounced precision-recall imbalances and frequent misclassifications. This suggests that LLMs struggle with subtle or ambiguous emotions that humans, despite some variation, handle more reliably.

Additionally, when interpreting correctness, it is important to note that our LLM annotation process was designed to rely on independent LLM instances, without mechanisms for dis-

TABLE VI
COST-EFFICIENCY ANALYSIS (AVERAGE PER ANNOTATOR)

Metric	Annotator	Guidelines	Iteration ($n=100$)	All ($n=1112$)
Time	Ann _i	11.4'	38.4'	427.0'
	GPT _i	-	2.9'	31.9'
	Mistral _i	-	2.2'	24.7'
	Gemini _i	-	5.2'	57.9'
Cost	Ann _i	7.17 €	24.14 €	268.4 €
	GPT _i	1.34 €	0.10 €	1.15 €
	Mistral _i	1.30 €	0.07 €	0.83 €
	Gemini _i	0.06 €	<0.01 €	0.05 €

discussion or disagreement resolution, unlike human annotators in our study. As a result, 39 sentences (3.5%) in LLM agreement (LLM_A) were left without an assigned label, since inter-LLM discussions, akin to human deliberation, were beyond the scope of this study. Similarly, before discussion, human annotations led to 34 sentences (3.1%) without an assigned label, which were later resolved through deliberation. Integrating discussion mechanisms into LLM annotation workflows could enhance performance [60], particularly for ambiguous emotions where disagreement is more prevalent.

2) *Cost-efficiency Analysis*: Table VI compares the cost-efficiency of human and LLM-based annotators⁷. For better comparability, the table reports average time and cost per annotator. For human annotators (Ann_i), we compute the average across the three annotators participating in each iteration. For LLM annotators (GPT_i , $Mistral_i$, $Gemini_i$), we take the average across the three annotation runs. On average, a human annotator takes more than $7\times$ longer to annotate the whole dataset (≈ 7 hours) than the slowest LLM-based annotator⁸, Gemini (≈ 1 hour). Cost disparity is even more pronounced – on average, one human annotator is $233\times$ more expensive⁹ than the most costly LLM annotator, GPT-4o. These findings highlight the scalability of LLM-based annotation, offering a cost-effective alternative to manual annotation, particularly for iterative and large-scale annotation tasks.

V. DISCUSSION

A. Research Questions

1) *Which taxonomy of emotions is most suitable for annotating mobile app reviews? (RQ₁)*: We establish Plutchik’s emotion taxonomy as the most effective framework for annotating mobile app reviews due to its structured categorization and relevance to key app-related emotions. Our selection is grounded by a systematic literature review (see Section IV-A), focusing on emotion popularity, frequency, and relevance to our domain, particularly for emotions such as *Anticipation*, which helps identify feature requests; *Trust*, which aligns with user goals and experiences; and *Disgust*, which signals critical issues leading to user rejection of an app or feature. While

our study is based on this taxonomy, the proposed framework is fully adaptable. Researchers can refine annotation guidelines (RQ₂) and modify input/output formats for LLM-based annotation (RQ₄). Additionally, while our focus is on emotions in app reviews, the literature review was conducted within the broader scope of software analysis. While our guidelines and taxonomy adaptations are tailored to the mobile app context (RQ₂), the same approach could be extended to other software-related user feedback domains, such as software product reviews or issue tracking systems.

2) *How can the selected taxonomy be effectively adapted to the specific context of app reviews? (RQ₂)*: Our adaptation of Plutchik’s taxonomy addresses the unique characteristics of mobile app reviews by combining structured guidelines with practical examples (Table I, Section IV-B). The dataset illustrates how these guidelines can be applied effectively, supporting both replication of our study and reuse of our guidelines and dataset in future research.

Developing clear, practical and unambiguous annotation criteria proved essential. To enhance practical usability, we iteratively refined our guidelines based on feedback from human discussions (RQ₃), incorporating disambiguations, additional examples, and specific criteria to distinguish overlapping emotions. For instance, we established clear distinctions between *Sadness* and *Surprise* (disappointment vs. unexpectedness) and *Joy* and *Trust* (appraisal vs. user engagement), helping annotators make more consistent decisions. Finally, our findings suggest that merging closely related emotions into broader categories could enhance classification performance while preserving interpretability.

3) *What challenges arise when annotating app reviews with emotional labels? (RQ₃)*: We identified four key challenges in emotion annotation (see Section IV-C). While these challenges primarily pertain to human annotation, they are also assessed in the context of LLM-based automated annotation (see discussion on RQ₄). These challenges serve as groundwork for identifying design strategies to support automated emotion extraction approaches. Mainly, we propose the following:

- 1) **Incorporating confidence scores and human-in-the-loop mechanisms** to prioritize high-certainty emotions while flagging low-certainty predictions. This mitigates the difficulty of defining boundaries between contiguous emotions (*Challenge 1*) and helps establish thresholds for subtle emotional intensity by reducing overinterpretation and underreporting (*Challenge 3*).
- 2) **Leveraging attention-based architectures** (e.g., BERT [61]) with **explainability techniques** (e.g., SHAP [62]) to improve transparency and traceability of mixed or conflicting emotions. This ensures better interpretability of overlapping emotional signals within a single sentence (*Challenge 2*).
- 3) **Employing context-enhanced input pipelines** that integrate full reviews and external metadata (e.g., app name, category, or user rating) to improve emotion prediction accuracy. This helps address the lack of context and

⁷Extended results per annotator are included in the replication package.

⁸LLM annotators integrate annotation guidelines as system prompts during each iteration; therefore, guideline processing time is not reported.

⁹Based on the average hourly cost of the five annotators.

linguistic ambiguities that hinder sentence-level emotion extraction (*Challenge 4*).

- 4) **Using multi-label classifiers or ensembles of binary classifiers** to better capture complex emotional expressions. This ensures that non-mutually exclusive emotions can be effectively modeled, particularly when multiple emotions co-occur in the same sentence (*Challenge 2*).

4) *How does LLM-based annotation compare to human annotation in emotion classification for app reviews? (RQ₄):* While LLMs provide a cost-effective alternative, human annotation remains the most reliable reference point, reinforcing their role as ground truth. Although LLMs exhibit internal consistency, they do not perfectly align with human interpretations, needing calibration or fine-tuning for domain-specific tasks. Using LLM annotations as a substitute for human annotation requires validation, as their agreement with human labels is moderate but not exact.

LLM-based agreement and correctness assessment demonstrates that the challenges affecting human annotation (RQ₃) also apply to LLMs. Poor performance in *Anger* and *Disgust* correlates with the difficulty of delineating overlapping negative emotions (*Challenge 1*). Similarly, frequent misclassification of *Surprise* suggests ambiguity in emotional intensity and context, reflecting human annotators’ struggles in defining arousal thresholds (*Challenge 3*). Furthermore, the instability in low-precision classes highlights the limitations of sentence-level annotation without broader contextual cues, emphasizing the need for context-enhanced pipelines (*Challenge 4*).

Although we evaluate LLM correctness relative to a human-annotated ground truth (Ann_A), our study does not assess the performance of LLMs in fully automated emotion extraction within user feedback analysis pipelines. Instead, we focus on the accuracy of LLMs as an alternative to human annotators, examining the cognitive challenges and limitations humans face when constructing foundational resources (e.g., an annotated dataset) for emotion classification.

Future research can reuse our dataset (Ann_A) to support automatic emotion extraction in various LLM-based settings. Encoder-only LLMs, such as BERT, RoBERTa, or XLNet, could be applied in a supervised text classification setting. Alternatively, decoder-only – generative – LLMs could be employed via fine-tuning or few-shot prompt engineering using partial subsets of our dataset. Further investigations should explore and compare multiple LLM-based annotation strategies, capitalizing on the ground truth, challenges, and design recommendations derived from this study.

B. Research Goal and Implications

Our study showcases how fine-grained emotion analysis in mobile app reviews faces three core limitations: (1) the lack of domain-adapted taxonomies, (2) the ambiguity in human interpretation of emotion labels, and (3) the uncertain reliability of automated methods. Our study directly addresses these limitations by operationalizing a widely accepted taxonomy (i.e., Plutchik’s) for the mobile app domain, developing annotation guidelines that clarify emotion boundaries with domain-

specific examples, and empirically demonstrating where LLMs align or diverge from human annotation. These contributions not only make emotion classification more feasible and interpretable but also expose the practical constraints and design trade-offs in scaling annotation processes—offering grounded insight for future tool development and dataset construction.

As a result, our study unlocks new opportunities in traditional RE tasks within the context of opinion mining from app stores. Our contributions (i.e., annotation guidelines, dataset, automated annotation pipelines) serve as groundwork for building (semi-)automatic pipelines for more precise categorization of user feedback, enabling a diversity of use cases that can be explored by leveraging the artifacts resulting from this research—such as feature-emotion pair sentiment analysis (UC₁), emotionally-oriented user segmentation for release planning (UC₂), and fine-grained issue prioritization (UC₃). The analysis of the generated dataset (RQ₂) and the challenges identified during its generation (RQ₃) demonstrate how emotional labels such as *Anticipation*, *Trust*, *Surprise*, or *Fear* offer extended knowledge dimensions compared to traditional polarity-based approaches. Furthermore, emotion analysis not only conveys the insights captured by polarity (i.e., positive, negative) and review type (i.e., bug report, feature request, praise [3]) classification pipelines, but also expands on additional emotional dimensions (e.g., *Surprise*, *Fear*, *Trust*) that might otherwise be neglected.

C. Threats to Validity

Concerning threats to validity [63], annotators relied on the full review to resolve linguistic ambiguities, which may have introduced unintended dependencies on contextual information. While this approach improved consistency, it also introduced the risk that certain emotional cues may have been interpreted differently when considering broader review contexts. Additionally, personal bias during human annotation posed a threat, particularly when annotators encountered ambiguous or overlapping emotional expressions. While involving five annotators and the generation, discussion, and refinement of the guidelines reduced this risk, differences in annotator interpretations may still have led to slight variations in the annotated dataset. Furthermore, annotation challenges such as distinguishing subtle variations in intensity and resolving conflicting emotions (e.g., *Joy* vs. *Trust*, *Sadness* vs. *Disgust*) may have affected annotation reliability. To address this, we specifically addressed these challenges through dedicated discussions and mitigation actions to improve the guidelines. Furthermore, we report these challenges to assist further research in considering the limitations of our dataset properly.

The selection of Plutchik’s taxonomy might not fully capture all possible emotional states present in app reviews. We mitigated this risk by conducting a thorough literature review before selecting the taxonomy. In addition, as our research design remains agnostic to a specific taxonomy, our replication package enables adaptation to alternative emotion taxonomies and annotation schemes. Another limitation from the annota-

tion process is the assessment of emotional intensity, as subtle arousal variations remain difficult to measure consistently.

Finally, our dataset may not generalize to all app review domains. Although reviews span diverse categories and features, further validation is needed to assess applicability across other domains, languages, and cultural contexts. Linguistic differences and user demographics may affect how emotions are conveyed in app reviews, suggesting the need for cross-domain evaluation. Regarding LLM selection, our results may not fully generalize to other architectures or newer models. Exploring alternatives like DeepSeek (with restricted API access during this research) or OpenAI reasoning models (e.g., o1), now available via API, could yield different outcomes, potentially improving agreement or introducing new annotation biases.

VI. RELATED WORK

A. Emotion Annotation of App Reviews

The use of multi-class, fine-grained emotion taxonomies in app reviews remains limited, though some related work exists. Riccosan published an Indonesian dataset of app reviews annotated with Parrott’s taxonomy [37]. While relatively large (20K reviews), it is not available in English. Moreover, their annotation relied on two annotators, reporting a Cohen’s Kappa of 0.61. They lack details on disagreement resolution and insights into how specific emotions were adapted to the app review domain. Moreover, emotions like *Anticipation* and *Trust*, relevant to app reviews, are not considered.

Several studies have explored methods for inferring emotions from app reviews using proprietary datasets. Malgaonkar et al. developed a tool integrating a WordNet-based lexicon method to identify Ekman’s emotions from a dataset of 53K reviews [54]. Similarly, Keertipati et al. applied a lexicon-based method using the LIWC dictionary for three negative emotions to analyse their correlation with app features [53]. Singh et al. manually annotated 2K mobile learning app reviews using also a lexicon-based approach aligned with Plutchik’s taxonomy [52], linking emotions to review descriptors like ratings, technical quality and usefulness. Beyond lexicon-based methods, Savarimuthu et al. employed IBM Watson’s Tone Analyzer to extract emotions as descriptors for assessing data waste in mobile app reviews [58]. Lastly, Cabellos et al. [55] manually analysed video game reviews using Liew & Turtle’s taxonomy to align emotions with moral aspects. However, these datasets are unavailable, lack emotion annotations, and do not evaluate extraction methods empirically. This underscores the relevance of emotion analysis but highlights the scarcity of annotated datasets.

B. LLM-based Annotation

The potential of LLMs for human-like reasoning tasks, combined with the need for large domain-specific datasets to reduce hallucinations and errors, has driven research into their use as data annotators [46]. Heseltine et al. analysed the performance of multiple annotation runs using OpenAI’s GPT-4 for political text annotation [64]. Their findings suggest that while LLM-assisted tagging achieves high accuracy for

simple tasks in cost-efficient settings, it struggles with complex and subjective analyses, such as sentiment annotation, where interpretation often varies between annotators [65]. Similarly, Sayeed et al. evaluated Gemini for text classification in materials science, reaching comparable conclusions [66]. Research has further explored LLM annotation across various fields, including mathematics [67], finance [68], and linguistics [69].

To address these limitations, Kim et al. proposed MEGAnno+ [60], a *human-LLM* collaborative framework designed to enhance the reliability and robustness of LLM-generated labels. Their approach integrates a human-in-the-loop mechanism to verify LLM annotations, concluding that fully autonomous annotation remains prone to errors, requiring human oversight for reliability. Similar studies investigate additional dimensions, such as the explainability [70] and cost-effectiveness [71] of human-LLM collaboration in annotation tasks. While several domain-specific studies have been conducted, further research is needed to assess the reliability of these agents and explore improvements through alternative annotation mechanisms. To this end, and in line with our findings, hybrid approaches that combine expert validation with automated annotations may provide a balanced solution for generating datasets to support supervised extraction methods.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

Our study addresses key challenges in fine-grained emotion extraction from mobile app reviews, offering several contributions: (i) clear emotion annotation guidelines tailored to mobile app reviews, (ii) an annotated dataset that adapts Plutchik’s taxonomy to this domain, (iii) an explicit identification of key challenges in this task, and (iv) a comparison between human and LLM-based annotations to assess the feasibility of scalable, automated annotation using LLMs. Together, these insights and data-based resources are readily available to support future research and advance progress in this field.

Future work will focus on automating emotion extraction using LLMs and mitigating data imbalance. We plan to explore fine-tuned encoder-based models (e.g., BERT, RoBERTa) and evaluate generative LLMs with few-shot learning and retrieval-augmented generation. Additionally, we will investigate data augmentation techniques such as synthetic data generation and paraphrasing to improve classifier robustness. Overall, our work sets the stage for improving automated emotion extraction through enhanced models and data strategies.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Full datasets, annotations, agreement results, and code for LLM-based annotation are available at <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.28548638>.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work has been supported by funding from the HIVE-MIND project – Horizon Europe call HORIZON-CL4-2024-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01 under Grant Agreement Number 101189745. This paper has been funded by the Spanish Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación under project/funding scheme PID2020-117191RB-I00 / AEI/10.13039/501100011033.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Dabrowski, E. Letier, A. Perini, and A. Susi, "Analysing app reviews for software engineering: a systematic literature review," *Empirical Software Engineering*, vol. 27, no. 2, p. 43, Jan 2022.
- [2] Jacek Dabrowski and Emmanuel Letier and Anna Perini and Angelo Susi, "Mining and searching app reviews for requirements engineering: Evaluation and replication studies," *Information Systems*, vol. 114, p. 102181, 2023.
- [3] W. Maalej and H. Nabil, "Bug report, feature request, or simply praise? on automatically classifying app reviews," in *2015 IEEE 23rd International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE)*, 2015, pp. 116–125.
- [4] M. Tushev, F. Ebrahimi, and A. Mahmoud, "Domain-specific analysis of mobile app reviews using keyword-assisted topic models," in *2022 IEEE/ACM 44th International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE)*, 2022, pp. 762–773.
- [5] M. Dragoni, M. Federici, and A. Rexha, "An unsupervised aspect extraction strategy for monitoring real-time reviews stream," *Information Processing & Management*, vol. 56, no. 3, pp. 1103–1118, 2019.
- [6] D. Pagano and W. Maalej, "User feedback in the appstore: An empirical study," in *2013 21st IEEE International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE)*, 2013, pp. 125–134.
- [7] A. A. Al-Subaihini, F. Sarro, S. Black, L. Capra, and M. Harman, "App store effects on software engineering practices," *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*, vol. 47, no. 2, pp. 300–319, 2021.
- [8] N. Alturaief, H. Aljamaan, and M. Baslyman, "Aware: Aspect-based sentiment analysis dataset of apps reviews for requirements elicitation," in *2021 36th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineering Workshops (ASEW)*, 2021, pp. 211–218.
- [9] E. Guzman and W. Maalej, "How do users like this feature? a fine grained sentiment analysis of app reviews," in *2014 IEEE 22nd International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE)*, 2014, pp. 153–162.
- [10] E. Bakiu and E. Guzman, "Which feature is unusable? detecting usability and user experience issues from user reviews," in *Proceedings - 2017 IEEE 25th International Requirements Engineering Conference Workshops, REW 2017*, 2017, p. 182 – 187.
- [11] Dabrowski, Jacek and Letier, Emmanuel and Perini, Anna and Susi, Angelo, "Finding and analyzing app reviews related to specific features: A research preview," *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, vol. 11412 LNCS, p. 183 – 189, 2019.
- [12] E. Guzman and A. Paredes Rojas, "Gender and user feedback: An exploratory study," in *Gender and user feedback: An exploratory study*, vol. 2019-September, 2019, p. 381 – 385.
- [13] L. Yu, H. Wang, X. Luo, T. Zhang, K. Liu, J. Chen, H. Zhou, Y. Tang, and X. Xiao, "Towards automatically localizing function errors in mobile apps with user reviews," *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*, vol. 49, no. 4, pp. 1464–1486, 2023.
- [14] N. Alturayef, H. Aljamaan, and J. Hassine, "An automated approach to aspect-based sentiment analysis of apps reviews using machine and deep learning," *Automated Software Engineering*, vol. 30, no. 2, p. 30, Sep 2023.
- [15] A. Maroof, S. Wasi, S. I. Jami, and M. S. Siddiqui, "Aspect-based sentiment analysis for service industry," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 109 702–109 713, 2024.
- [16] Y. Gao, Z. Pan, H. Wang, and G. Chen, "Alexa, my love: Analyzing reviews of amazon echo," in *2018 IEEE SmartWorld, Ubiquitous Intelligence & Computing, Advanced & Trusted Computing, Scalable Computing & Communications, Cloud & Big Data Computing, Internet of People and Smart City Innovation (SmartWorld/SCALCOM/UIC/ATC/CBD-Com/IOP/SCI)*, 2018, pp. 372–380.
- [17] H. Sankar, V. Subramaniaswamy, V. Vijayakumar, S. Arun Kumar, R. Logesh, and A. Umamakeswari, "Intelligent sentiment analysis approach using edge computing-based deep learning technique," *Softw. Pract. Exp.*, vol. 50, no. 5, pp. 645–657, May 2020.
- [18] E.-R. Luțan and C. Bădică, "Emotion-based literature books recommender systems," in *Annals of Computer Science and Information Systems*, vol. 35. IEEE, Sep. 2023, pp. 275–280.
- [19] B. Lin, N. Cassee, A. Serebrenik, G. Bavota, N. Novielli, and M. Lanza, "Opinion mining for software development: A systematic literature review," *ACM Trans. Softw. Eng. Methodol.*, vol. 31, no. 3, Mar. 2022.
- [20] D. Hidellaarachchi, J. Grundy, R. Hoda, and I. Mueller, "The influence of human aspects on requirements engineering-related activities: Software practitioners' perspective," *ACM Trans. Softw. Eng. Methodol.*, vol. 32, no. 5, Jul. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3546943>
- [21] B. Cheng, C. Arora, X. Liu, T. Hoang, Y. Wang, and J. Grundy, "Multi-modal emotion recognition for enhanced requirements engineering: A novel approach," in *2023 IEEE 31st International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE)*, 2023, pp. 299–304.
- [22] K. Taveter, L. Sterling, S. Pedell, R. Burrows, and E. M. Taveter, "A method for eliciting and representing emotional requirements: Two case studies in e-healthcare," in *2019 IEEE 27th International Requirements Engineering Conference Workshops (REW)*, 2019, pp. 100–105.
- [23] Z. Shakeri Hossein Abad, V. Gervasi, D. Zowghi, and K. Barker, "Elica: An automated tool for dynamic extraction of requirements relevant information," in *2018 5th International Workshop on Artificial Intelligence for Requirements Engineering (AIRE)*, 2018, pp. 8–14.
- [24] A. Sutcliffe, P. Sawyer, and N. Bencomo, "The implications of 'soft' requirements," in *2022 IEEE 30th International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE)*, 2022, pp. 178–188.
- [25] A. Ferrari, T. Huichapa, P. Spoletini, N. Novielli, D. Fucci, and D. Girardi, "Using voice and biofeedback to predict user engagement during product feedback interviews," *ACM Trans. Softw. Eng. Methodol.*, vol. 33, no. 4, Apr. 2024.
- [26] A. F. Araujo, M. P. S. Gôlo, and R. M. Marcacini, "Opinion mining for app reviews: an analysis of textual representation and predictive models," *Automated Software Engg.*, vol. 29, no. 1, May 2022.
- [27] Y. Singh and P. K. Suri, "An empirical analysis of mobile learning app usage experience," *Technology in Society*, vol. 68, p. 101929, 2022.
- [28] N. D. Khan, J. Ali Khan, J. Li, T. Ullah, A. Alwadain, A. Yasin, and Q. Zhao, "How do crowd-users express their opinions against software applications in social media? a fine-grained classification approach," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 98 004–98 028, 2024.
- [29] A. d. Arriba, M. Oriol, and X. Franch, "Applying transfer learning to sentiment analysis in social media," in *2021 IEEE 29th International Requirements Engineering Conference Workshops (REW)*, 2021, pp. 342–348.
- [30] P. Ekman, "An argument for basic emotions," *Cognition and Emotion*, vol. 6, no. 3–4, pp. 169–200, 1992.
- [31] R. Plutchik, "The nature of emotions," *American Scientist*, vol. 89, no. 4, pp. 344–350, 2001. [Online]. Available: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/27857503>
- [32] W. G. Parrott, "Emotions in social psychology: Essential readings," W. G. Parrott, Ed. Philadelphia: Psychology Press, 2001, ch. 4, pp. 8–10.
- [33] J. S. Y. Liew, H. R. Turtle, and E. D. Liddy, "Emotweet-28: A fine-grained emotion corpus for sentiment analysis," in *Proceedings of the Tenth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC 2016)*, 2016, pp. 1149–1156. [Online]. Available: <https://aclanthology.org/L16-1183/>
- [34] Y. C. Hua, P. Denny, J. Wicker, and K. Taskova, "A systematic review of aspect-based sentiment analysis: Domains, methods, and trends," *Artificial Intelligence Review*, vol. 57, no. 11, p. 296, September 2024.
- [35] A. S. Cowen, "Mapping the passions: Toward a high-dimensional taxonomy of emotional experience and expression," *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 69–90, July 2019.
- [36] M. L. McHugh, "Interrater reliability: the kappa statistic," *Biochemia Medica*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 276–282, 2012. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3900052/>
- [37] Riccosan and K. E. Saputra, "Multilabel multiclass sentiment and emotion dataset from indonesian mobile application review," *Data in Brief*, vol. 50, p. 109576, 2023.
- [38] A. Simmons and L. Hoon, "Agree to disagree: on labelling helpful app reviews," in *Proceedings of the 28th Australian Conference on Computer-Human Interaction*, ser. OzCHI '16, 2016, p. 416–420.
- [39] Q. Motger, A. Miaschi, F. Dell'Orletta, X. Franch, and J. Marco, "T-frex: A transformer-based feature extraction method from mobile app reviews," in *2024 IEEE International Conference on Software Analysis, Evolution and Reengineering (SANER)*, 2024, pp. 227–238.
- [40] M. Hosseini, E. C. Groen, A. Shahri, and R. Ali, "Craft: A crowd-annotated feedback technique," in *2017 IEEE 25th International Requirements Engineering Conference Workshops (REW)*, 2017, pp. 170–175.

- [41] M. van Vliet, E. C. Groen, F. Dalpiaz, and S. Brinkkemper, "Identifying and classifying user requirements in online feedback via crowdsourcing," in *Requirements Engineering: Foundation for Software Quality: 26th International Working Conference, REFSQ 2020, Pisa, Italy, March 24–27, 2020, Proceedings*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag, 2020, p. 143–159.
- [42] C. Stanik, M. Haering, C. Jesdabodi, and W. Maalej, "Which app features are being used? learning app feature usages from interaction data," in *2020 IEEE 28th International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE)*, 2020, pp. 66–77.
- [43] A. Malpani, S. S. Vedula, C. C. G. Chen, and G. D. Hager, "A study of crowdsourced segment-level surgical skill assessment using pairwise rankings," *International Journal of Computer Assisted Radiology and Surgery*, vol. 10, no. 9, pp. 1435–1447, 2015.
- [44] N. Alvaro, M. Conway, S. Doan, C. Lofi, J. Overington, and N. Collier, "Crowdsourcing twitter annotations to identify first-hand experiences of prescription drug use," *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, vol. 58, pp. 280–287, 2015.
- [45] T. S. Kim, A. Malpani, A. Reiter, G. D. Hager, S. Sikder, and S. Swaroop Vedula, "Crowdsourcing annotation of surgical instruments in videos of cataract surgery," in *Intravascular Imaging and Computer Assisted Stenting and Large-Scale Annotation of Biomedical Data and Expert Label Synthesis*, D. Stoyanov, Z. Taylor, S. Balocco, R. Sznitman, A. Martel, L. Maier-Hein, L. Duong, G. Zahnd, S. Demirci, S. Albarqouni, S.-L. Lee, S. Moriconi, V. Cheplygina, D. Mateus, E. Trucco, E. Granger, and P. Jannin, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2018, pp. 121–130.
- [46] X. Hou, Y. Zhao, Y. Liu, Z. Yang, K. Wang, L. Li, X. Luo, D. Lo, J. Grundy, and H. Wang, "Large language models for software engineering: A systematic literature review," *ACM Trans. Softw. Eng. Methodol.*, vol. 33, no. 8, Dec. 2024.
- [47] K. Guo, D. Diefenbach, A. Gourru, and C. Gravier, "Fine-tuning Strategies for Domain Specific Question Answering under Low Annotation Budget Constraints," in *2023 IEEE 35th International Conference on Tools with Artificial Intelligence (ICTAI)*. Los Alamitos, CA, USA: IEEE Computer Society, Nov. 2023, pp. 166–171.
- [48] J. Ashwin, A. Chhabra, and V. Rao, "Using large language models for qualitative analysis can introduce serious bias," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2309.17147>
- [49] A. Martín-Martín, M. Thelwall, E. Orduna-Malea, and E. Delgado López-Cózar, "Google scholar, microsoft academic, scopus, dimensions, web of science, and opencitations' coci: a multidisciplinary comparison of coverage via citations," *Scientometrics*, vol. 126, no. 1, pp. 871–906, 2021.
- [50] I. Pawełozek and J. Wiczorkowski, "Trip planning mobile application: a perspective case study of user experience," *Engineering Management in Production and Services*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 55–71, June 2023.
- [51] M. Shaheen, S. M. Awan, N. Hussain, and Z. A. Gondal, "Sentiment analysis on mobile phone reviews using supervised learning techniques," *International Journal of Modern Education and Computer Science (IJMECS)*, vol. 11, no. 7, pp. 32–43, 2019.
- [52] Y. Singh and P. K. Suri, "An empirical analysis of mobile learning app usage experience," *Technology in Society*, vol. 68, p. 101929, 2022.
- [53] S. Keertipati, B. T. R. Savarimuthu, and S. A. Licorish, "Approaches for prioritizing feature improvements extracted from app reviews," in *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering*, ser. EASE '16, 2016.
- [54] S. Malgaonkar, C. W. Lee, S. A. Licorish, B. T. R. Savarimuthu, and A. Tahir, "Appsent a tool that analyzes app reviews," 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1907.10191>
- [55] B. Cabellos, J. I. Pozo, K. Marín-Rubio *et al.*, "Do pro-social video games promote moral activity?: an analysis of user reviews of papers, please," *Education and Information Technologies*, vol. 27, pp. 11411–11442, 2022.
- [56] M. Valenzuela-Beltrán and M. D. Rodríguez, "How conversational agents are helping to take medications: Studying reviews of amazon echo," in *2021 Mexican International Conference on Computer Science (ENC)*, 2021, pp. 1–7.
- [57] A. G. Myers, "Content analysis of consumer reviews of the amazon echo dot 2nd and 3rd generations," Master's thesis, University of Wisconsin–Stout, 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://digital.library.wisc.edu/1793/79628>
- [58] B. Savarimuthu, J. Corbett, M. Yasir, and V. Lakshmi, "Improving information systems sustainability by applying machine learning to detect and reduce data waste," *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, vol. 53, pp. 189–213, 2023.
- [59] D. M. Berry, "Empirical evaluation of tools for hairy requirements engineering tasks," *Empirical Software Engineering*, vol. 26, no. 6, p. 111, August 2021.
- [60] H. Kim, K. Mitra, R. Li Chen, S. Rahman, and D. Zhang, "MEGAnno+: A human-LLM collaborative annotation system," in *Proceedings of the 18th Conference of the European Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: System Demonstrations*, N. Aletras and O. De Clercq, Eds. St. Julians, Malta: Association for Computational Linguistics, Mar. 2024, pp. 168–176.
- [61] J. Devlin, M.-W. Chang, K. Lee, and K. Toutanova, "BERT: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding," in *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies, Volume 1 (Long and Short Papers)*, J. Burstein, C. Doran, and T. Solorio, Eds. Minneapolis, Minnesota: Association for Computational Linguistics, Jun. 2019, pp. 4171–4186.
- [62] S. M. Lundberg and S.-I. Lee, "A unified approach to interpreting model predictions," in *Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems*, ser. NIPS'17. Red Hook, NY, USA: Curran Associates Inc., 2017, p. 4768–4777.
- [63] C. Wohlin, P. Runeson, M. Hst, M. C. Ohlsson, B. Regnell, and A. Wesslin, *Experimentation in Software Engineering*. Springer Publishing Company, Incorporated, 2012.
- [64] T. Heseltine and J. Hohenberg, "Large language models as a substitute for human experts in annotating political text," *Research & Politics*, vol. 11, no. 3, p. 20531680241236239, 2024.
- [65] T. Zhang, I. C. Irsan, F. Thung, and D. Lo, "Revisiting sentiment analysis for software engineering in the era of large language models," *ACM Trans. Softw. Eng. Methodol.*, vol. 34, no. 3, Feb. 2025.
- [66] H. M. Sayeed, T. Mohanty, and T. D. Sparks, "Annotating Materials Science Text: A Semi-automated Approach for Crafting Outputs with Gemini Pro," *Integrating Materials and Manufacturing Innovation*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 445–452, Jun 2024.
- [67] R. Shan and A. Youssef, "Using large language models to automate annotation and part-of-math tagging of math equations," in *Intelligent Computer Mathematics: 17th International Conference, CICM 2024, Montréal, QC, Canada, August 5–9, 2024, Proceedings*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag, 2024, p. 3–20.
- [68] T. D. Aguda, S. Siddagangappa, E. Kochkina, S. Kaur, D. Wang, and C. Smiley, "Large language models as financial data annotators: A study on effectiveness and efficiency," in *Proceedings of the 2024 Joint International Conference on Computational Linguistics, Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC-COLING 2024)*, May 2024, pp. 10124–10145. [Online]. Available: <https://aclanthology.org/2024.lrec-main.885/>
- [69] D. Yu, L. Li, H. Su, and M. Fuoli, "Assessing the potential of LLM-assisted annotation for corpus-based pragmatics and discourse analysis: The case of apology," *International Journal of Corpus Linguistics*, vol. 29, no. 4, pp. 534–561, December 2024.
- [70] X. Wang, H. Kim, S. Rahman, K. Mitra, and Z. Miao, "Human-llm collaborative annotation through effective verification of llm labels," in *Proceedings of the 2024 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, ser. CHI '24. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2024.
- [71] H. Rouzegar and M. Makrehchi, "Enhancing text classification through llm-driven active learning and human annotation," in *Proceedings of The 18th Linguistic Annotation Workshop (LAW-XVIII)*. Online: Association for Computational Linguistics, March 2024, pp. 98–111. [Online]. Available: <https://aclanthology.org/2024.law-1.10>